

Surveys to monitor the mental health of early-career researchers during the COVID-19 pandemic

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Purpose

The strong sanitary and economic effects, consequences and aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic are still with us. While the role of researchers gained more importance and respect in tackling the crisis and in finding solutions, much less attention had been paid on how the pandemic affected research, especially early- to mid-career researchers (EMCR). As soon as the first lockdown measures had been introduced, members of the Young Academy of Europe (YAE) published a letter (Husby and Modinos, 2020) in *Nature*, and the Hungarian Young Academy (HYA) released a [statement](#) and a white paper (Dékány et al. 2020) targeting decision-makers of funding bodies and institutions, in which they highlighted the particular vulnerability of young researchers amid the pandemic. Although many of the difficulties faced by researchers in precarious positions or in experimental science could be easily predicted, science-based evidence was required in order to clearly and scientifically address these issues, and to assess their impact on the mental health of EMCRs. Therefore, two surveys have been separately conducted by the YAE (Swider-Cios et al. 2021a, b) and the HYA (Németh et al. 2022) among EMCRs in 2020 and 2021, respectively.

Design

The YAE is an organization originally founded by ERC Starting Grant winners in 2012. Its approximately 160 members are high-profile young principal investigators in leadership positions. During our survey ran in 2020, 151 respondents (68% women, 31% men, 1% had a different gender or preferred not to disclose it) answered the approx. 20-min-long survey

designed with SoGoSurvey platform, and composed of 33 questions related to working conditions (15 questions), personal background (13 questions), and optional questions (4 questions). The entire anonymized dataset as well as the questions are available online (Swider-Cios et al. 2021, Srinivas et al. 2021).

The thorough, 40-min-long survey of the HYA was aimed at deciphering several aspects of the career prospects of Hungarian EMCRs, with only few questions related directly to the effect of COVID-19 on researchers (Németh et al. 2022). Many of these gathered information about which aspect of their work was mostly or least affected by the pandemic (e.g. conducting experiments, the publication writing process, etc.), but they also included questions related to the ability to manage work-life balance, or whether EMCRs felt isolated during the pandemic.

Results

Both survey datasets outlined that due to the various individual and personal situations of the EMCRs, unfunded and blanket extensions only increase the already existing inequalities of marginalized groups and minorities. These latter include those with carer responsibilities (especially mothers), those with low salary, those living in the capital (Budapest), those with university teaching duties, or those researchers who consider foreign research travelling (short-term professional study trips and visits and participation in international conferences) important for their own career progression and research (Németh et al. 2022). Women with carer responsibilities reported increased household work, sleep deprivation, and moderate stress during the lockdown period (Swider-Cios et al. 2021a, b).

Our investigations clearly revealed a differential pattern among EMCRs when self-reporting about the effect of the pandemic on their work-life balance (Németh et al. 2022). Significantly larger proportion of women, scientific parents and university lecturers “strongly agreed” on having difficulties to reconcile their work and private life, while those without children “strongly disagreed” with the same statement. A larger proportion of researchers (46%) felt that they spent less time with research activities during the lockdown, while 39% spent more time with research than before. A majority of our respondents felt professionally isolated during the pandemic, especially those with children. The above data clearly outline that mental health of EMCRs was strongly affected by the pandemic. However, in several institutions no measures have been taken to support those in need. We have also shown that inequalities in career prospects and progression clearly differed between researchers with and without caring and household responsibilities (especially mothers).

Implications

Science for policy should always first involve an important step of gathering data in order to be able to provide evidence-based advice for the decision makers about how to mitigate the negative impacts of COVID-19 on the career prospects of EMCRs. We argue for mental health support in academia and for measures taking into account lockdown periods as career breaks for those with caring responsibilities. More differentiated response towards grant extensions is necessary, because blanket extensions are only strengthening the existing inequalities and gender bias, and may benefit already privileged groups.

In collaboration with the Researcher Mental Health Observatory COST Action (ReMO), the YAE, along with other stakeholders, took part in the organization of the [4th GAGO Conference on European Science Policy](#) in 2022, and in drafting a [Manifesto](#) raising awareness about the situation of EMCRs and their mental wellbeing. As a follow-up on the handing over of the Manifesto to Commissioner Mariya Gabriel on 10th January 2023 in Brussels, where she announced her will to provide “partnership” and support for early-career researchers, the ERA Research Careers Team of the European Commission launched consultations with various academic stakeholders from member states about delivering a package in support of (early-career) researchers in which we are also represented.

In addition to releasing a Hungarian and English statement, publishing a white paper, the members of the HYA directly contacted national funding bodies and asked for grant extension possibilities for EMCRs, and conducted a large-scale survey including questions related to mental health. Considering the situation of EMCRs in Hungary, we also launched a webinar series about mental health. The 2021 [webinar](#) introducing ReMO and soliciting discussion about work-life balance in academia, as well as the [webinar](#) about workaholism and burnout in academia were very well attended events. This shows that similar programs are warmly welcomed by the research community, and open discussion about these topics may help to reduce stigmata and to foster a more healthy academic culture and ecosystem.

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Resources

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